

The Effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Romanian Tourist Sector

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is considered one of the most important economic sectors, due to its multiple roles, namely: economic, social, cultural, educational and political role. The tourism also is considered to be one of the most important sectors for supporting and developing a country's economic through the fact that people have traveled for a long period of time and still continue to do it also nowadays more often. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused several global damages and has spread rapidly, affecting all the sectors, and especially the tourism one. The development of this sector is closely linked to the ability of people to travel, which is why the restrictions imposed by the authorities for stopping the virus to spread, have reduced seriously the evolution of the tourism. The purpose of this paper is to reflect the effects of the pandemic on the Romanian tourism, and, at the same time, to highlight the relevance and the sensibility of this sector crisis events. This article analyzes the situation of the tourism in Romania, both in the pre-pandemic period and during it, following the number of international arrivals and the tourism receipts, but also the evolution of the establishments of tourist reception with accommodation functions. The data provided by the World Tourism Organization (UNTWO), World Health Organization (WHO), the World Bank and the National Institute of Statistics (INS) were used in order to observe the impact of the pandemic on the Romanian tourism, and the research was based on the analysis and interpretation of the obtained data. As a conclusion, in the end, the effects of the pandemic and the impact that the possible crisis situations have on the Romanian touristic sector can be observed.

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic had an important influence over the tourism industry, as this sector is closely linked to the ability of people to travel, which is why the restrictions introduced by the authorities for stopping the virus to spread, have reduced seriously the evolution of the tourism. In 2020, on most of the global destinations, the United Nations World Tourism Organization reported total restrictions for travelling. As a result, the tourism sector suffered more than other industries and it was affected on a large scale.

Like worldwide, Romania's tourism was also affected by the pandemic and the measures that were taken to stop spreading the coronavirus. In this context, the

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paper tries to reflect the effects of the pandemic on the Romanian tourism, and, at the same time, to highlight the relevance and the sensibility of this sector crisis events. This article analyzes the situation of the tourism in Romania, both in the pre-pandemic period and during it, following the number of international arrivals and the tourism receipts, but also the evolution of the establishments of tourist reception with accommodation functions.

2. Literature Review

Research on the effects of COVID-19 on the global tourism are present in the existing literature. Also, many reports by World Travel and Tourism Council and World Organization of Tourism have identified the impact of the pandemic on the tourism sector.

Tourism is an important sector in the global economy and has an important contribution to the world's GDP (more than 10%) and 30% of the world's export services. The pandemic had affected seriously the tourism sector, thus influencing the economic development of many countries in the world.

Due to the pandemic, the tourism industry registered globally a loss of over 820 billion USD (Ozili & Arun, 2020). All these impacted the tourism industry due to the policies of stay at home and social distancing imposed by the governments. Ahikul et al. (2020) revealed that coronavirus significantly influenced the Chinese tourism industry. Besides China, the United States were affected by the rapid spread of COVID-19 (Farzanegan et al., 2020). The attractive touristic destinations, like France, Italy and Spain had also suffered from the pandemic, as the virus had an impact over the global tourism (Estrada et al., 2020). Other articles, Hoque et al. (2020), Dinarto et al. (2020), and Deb and Nafi (2020), researched the impact of COVID-19 on Indonesia and Bangladesh. The SARS epidemic was the most influential disease in the tourism industry, as it restricted international air travel for six months (IATA, 2020).

The tourism was affected in each country differently, depending on the spreading of the virus and the correlation between the economic development and the tourism compared to each sector of the economy (Altuntas & Gök, 2021).

Like worldwide, Romania's tourism has been hardly hit by the pandemic. It was observed that COVID-19 has produced dramatic effects for the tourism industry, and Romanian businesses have not been bypassed (Gheorghiescu, 2020). The impact of the pandemic over the Romanian tourism was analyzed in several articles (Popescu et al., 2022; Popescu, 2021; Volkmann et al., 2021), that took into consideration the effect over the tourism offer and demand, over the Romanian flows and over the tourism business.

3. Methodology

For this study, the factors that were taken into consideration have been the following ones:

- international tourist arrivals and receipts;

- arrivals of tourist by type of tourist (Romanian and foreigners) and means of transportation (road, air, railway, naval);
- number of accommodation establishments and occupancy rate (total, by type of unit).

The empirical data provided by the World Tourism Organization (UNTWO) and the National Institute of Statistics (NIS) were used in order to observe the impact of the pandemic on the Romanian tourism. Based on this data, the analysis of the tourism sector is divided into two periods: before COVID-19 period (2010-2019) and during the COVID-19 period (2019-2021). As a conclusion, in the end, the effects of the pandemic and the impact that the possible crisis situations have on the Romanian touristic sector can be observed.

4. Results and Discussion

The pandemic with the SARS-CoV-2 virus had strong effects on Romania, so that the first case was registered on February 26, 2020, and by March 23, 2021, the total number of confirmed cases would be of 900.858, and the number of registered deaths to be 22.268, as seen in Fig. 1 (WHO, 2021).

Fig. 1. Total number of cases/ deaths (March 2021)

Source: World Health Organization (2021)

4.1. The tourism sector before the pandemic (2010-2019)

Between 2010 and 2019, tourism experienced a steady growth, as the number of arrivals of international tourists increased from 6.07 million in 2010 to 13.37 million in 2019. As it can be observed in Fig. 2, in the year 2011 the international arrivals of tourists increased by 15.79% from 6.07 million in 2010 to 7.03 million. The growth trend continued up to 2019, with the highest increased in 2015 (17.19%) compared to 2014.

Fig. 2. International tourist arrivals (millions)
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

Over the period 2010-2019, international tourism industry receipts registered significant increase from 1.63 billion USD in 2010 to 4.24 billion USD in 2019 (Fig. 3). The largest decline during the observed period was recorded in 2015 of 6.69% and the largest increase in 2017 of 43.72%, from 2.47 billion USD up to 3.55 billion USD (World Tourism Organization, 2021).

Fig. 3. International tourist receipts (USD billion)
Source: World Tourism Organization (2021a, 2021b)

As for the type of tourist it can be observed that for the analyzed period the Romanian tourists represent the majority (78.1%) compared to the foreigners (21.9%), with low yearly fluctuations (Fig. 3). Based on the statistics, it can be said that Romania is not yet a destination that can attract international visitors, but, on the other hand, it is a good offer for the domestic tourists, in order to find more about their own country and to discover its beauties.

Fig. 4. Arrivals of tourist, by type of tourist
Source: Author's calculation

Primary data: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

The period 2010-2019 was also significant in terms of the means of transport used by tourists when travelling (Table 1). This is a very important aspect in terms of accessibility, so tourists chose to travel mostly by road transport (76%), followed by air transport (20.1%), naval (2%) and railway transport (1.9%). The air transport started to register an important weight from 2016, due to the low cost flights and to the development of several Romanian airports. As for the decrease of the naval and railway transport during the last analyzed years (2015-2019), this happened because of the bad existing infrastructure, the relative high costs and the long time for traveling.

Table 1. Arrivals of foreign tourist, by means of transport

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
With road means of transport	78.8%	74.6%	75.9%	77.9%	75.7%	80.1%	75.1%	73.2%	73.7%	74.5%
With railway means of transport	3.0%	3.4%	3.2%	2.9%	2.0%	1.5%	1.2%	1.1%	1.0%	1.1%
With air means of transport	16.2%	19.8%	18.5%	16.8%	20.0%	16.5%	22.1%	24.2%	23.9%	22.9%
With naval means of transport	2.1%	2.2%	2.3%	2.4%	2.2%	1.9%	1.6%	1.5%	1.4%	1.4%

Source: Author's calculation

Primary data: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

Another important aspect when taking into consideration the tourism sector is related to the accommodation establishments that can offer shelter to the tourists. In Romania, during the analyzed period, the total number of units fluctuated yearly (Fig. 5), registering the highest decrease in 2011 (4.19%) and the highest increase in 2016 (16.35%).

Fig. 5. Total number of accommodation establishments
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

Regarding the evolution of each type of accommodation establishment, in Fig. 6, it can be observed that in 2019 compared with 2010 most of the establishments had an increase, with little exceptions, like inns, touristic villas and camps. The highest decrease from the camps is due to the closing of most of the state owned units because of the lack of tourists and the high demand for the private camps that most of the times offer accommodation in existing boarding houses.

As for the increase registered by the hostels, this is due to the young people travelling to Romania for different festivals. Another type of unit that had an upward trend is the agro touristic boarding houses that are offering specific services and activities that attract both the foreigners and the domestic tourists.

Fig. 6. Accommodation establishments - 2019 over 2010 (%)
Source: Author's calculation
Primary data: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

The occupancy rate during the analyzed period (Fig. 7) was on an upward trend, with the highest value observed in 2019 (37.5%). The establishments that are over the average total occupancy rate are the hotels (46.8%) and apartment hotels (47.5%), thing that is also due to the development of the business tourism that represent a high weight for Romania (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Accommodation establishments, by occupancy rate (2010-2019)
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

Fig. 8. Accommodation establishments, by occupancy rate and type of establishment
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2020)

4.2. Tourism during the pandemic (2019-2021)

The year 2020 was an atypical year for the Romanian tourism. The evolution of the pandemic and all the restrictions imposed by the government determined tourists to change their behavior. According to the statistics, in 2020, the international tourist arrivals reached 6.4 million in Romania, with a 52.16% decrease compared to 2019. The situation gets better in 2021, when the number of international arrivals reached 9.37 million, with a rise of 46.44% compared to the previous year and drop of 29.94% compared to 2019 (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. International tourist arrivals (millions)
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

From the point of view of the receipts from the tourism industry that were recorded in 2020 (Fig. 10) for Romania, the value decreased by 62.26%. After the restrictions were more relaxed and the tourists started to travel again, the receipts started to recover and be close to the value from 2019, with a drop of 22.17% compared to this year.

Fig. 10. International tourist receipts (USD billion)
Source: World Tourism Organization (2021a, 2021b)

As mention above, even if the foreign tourist did not visit Romania so much anymore, the Romanians are the most important source of tourists, representing over 90% of the total number of tourists. The year 2020 was not a favorable one for the incoming tourism, due to the restrictions imposed. The foreign tourists represented only 7.1% in 2020, with a high decrease from 2019. The year 2021, came with a slight recovery as the number of foreign tourist started to increase, reaching 9% (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Arrivals of tourist, by type of tourist

Source: Author's calculation

Primary data: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

The pandemic period also affected the means of transport (Table 2). The road transport remained on the first place in the preferences of the tourist and also increased, especially in 2020, representing 82.6%. In terms of air and railway means of transport, both registered a decrease compared with 2019, due to the lockdowns, cancellation of flights or the tourists' fear of travelling in congested means of transport.

Besides the road means of transport, where people traveled only with the family and were able to respect the hygiene measures, also the naval transportation had a slight upward.

Table 2. Arrivals of foreign tourist, by means of transport

	2019	2020	2021
With road means of transport	74.5%	82.6%	79.1%
With railway means of transport	1.1%	0.9%	0.7%
With air means of transport	22.9%	14.5%	17.0%
With naval means of transport	1.4%	2.0%	3.2%

Source: Author's calculation

Primary data: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

A positive effect of the pandemic, besides the increase of the domestic tourism, was the increase of accommodation establishments (Fig. 12). Another effect of the pandemic was the change of tourists' behavior and demands when talking about choosing the destinations and the types of establishments. They became more interested in travelling away for the crowded cities, in rural areas that assure a safe

stay. This led to the increase in number of establishments, especially in small units, with small number of rooms, which can offer a wide range of activities in fresh air (Table 3).

Fig. 12. Total number of accommodation establishments
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

Table 3. Accommodation establishments – change over previous year (%)

	2020	2021
Hotels	-1.68%	0.13%
Hostels	1.55%	1.22%
Apartment hotels	5.88%	27.78%
Motels	-2.28%	0.47%
Inns	0.00%	0.00%
Touristic villas	6.06%	0.00%
Touristic chalets	1.80%	-1.77%
Bungalows	-17.77%	9.83%
Holiday villages	-11.11%	0.00%
Camping	5.17%	9.84%
Touristic halting places	-8.51%	2.33%
Houselet type unit	12.20%	21.74%
School and pre-school camps	-12.73%	8.33%
Touristic boarding houses	3.59%	0.93%
Agro touristic boarding houses	7.93%	14.49%
Ships accommodation spaces	12.50%	-7.41%

Source: Author's calculation

Primary data: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

The tourism was both in 2020 and 2021 an alternative for the Romanians to spend their holidays or week-ends in safe places. Even so the occupancy rate during the pandemic decreased due to the imposed restrictions and the cancelation of reservations (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Accommodation establishments, by occupancy rate (2019-2021)
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

After the relaxations of safety measures, most of the tourists became more oriented towards guesthouses. Due to all these, the occupancy rate that guest houses, camping, agro touristic boarding houses has increased during 2020-2021 (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Accommodation establishments, by occupancy rate and type of establishment
Source: National Institute of Statistics (2022)

5. Conclusion

Like in other countries worldwide, also in Romania, the tourism was affected by the pandemic in 2020, but started to recover step by step in 2021. The main aspects analyzed in this paper are the following:

- the number of arrivals decreased by about 53% in 2020 and afterwards increased by about 47% in 2021 compared to 2020;

- the tourist receipts dropped by 62% in 2020 and afterwards recovered in 2021, getting close to the value from 2019;
- the Romanian tourists dominated the domestic tourist with a weight of 92%, even if their number was smaller by 45% in 2020 and 21% in 2021 compared to 2019;
- the foreign tourists declined by 83.08% in 2020 compared to 2019 and after increased in 2021 compared to 2020 by 85.7%;
- the total number of accommodation establishments registered an upward trend yearly, especially the small units, with small number of rooms, which can offer a wide range of activities in fresh air, which also had a positive trend from the occupancy rate point of view;
- the general trend for the occupancy rate dropped initially, in 2020, by about 53% and then increase in 2021 compared to 2020 by 43.58%;
- the restrictions imposed by the pandemic affected a lot the tourism sector, and a part of units were even closed or failed.

As a final conclusion, the pandemic had both positive and negative impact over the Romanian tourism. The positive effects offer strategies for recovering the tourists' confidence and encourage the upskilling tourism, the digitization of the ecosystem and the protection of the environment.

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